

INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION AND TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The article reveals the meaning of intercultural communication. The interdependence of teaching foreign languages and intercultural communication in the professional training of specialists in the field of translation.

Keywords: intercultural communication, foreign world, foreign culture, communicative competence.

Intercultural communication is not only a science, but also a set of skills that can and should be owned. First of all, these skills are needed by those whose professional activity is associated with the interaction between cultures, when mistakes and communication failures lead to other failures - in negotiations, inefficient work of the team, to social tension. Thus, against the background of ever-increasing interest in the study of cultures of different peoples, close attention to the issues of intercultural communication, the task teacher to teach not only to understand a foreign language and speak it, but also to give specific knowledge about the characteristics of a particular culture in the field of professional, social and partly interpersonal communication. The result of the effectiveness of such training programs is a dialogue of cultures, mutual understanding, tolerance and respect for culture of communication partners.

Professional knowledge is always practical, but the degree of fluency in it and the possibility of developing specific skills and abilities directly depends on the strength of knowledge of theoretical foundations. Translation activity is one of the branches of philology. "Because language is the mirror of culture, the treasury of culture, the transmitter, the tool and instrument of culture, solving the actual problem of teaching a foreign language as means of communication between representatives of different peoples is that languages should be studied in unity with the world and culture of the peoples speaking this language" [1, 78].

The close relationship and interdependence of teaching foreign languages and intercultural communications are so obvious that they hardly need lengthy explanations [3, 5].

Intercultural communicative competence of an interpreter consists of:

- sociolinguistic competence (selection, use and understanding of linguistic forms depending on social strata, social groups, dialects, etc.);
- socio-cultural competence (informational competence, regional competence, cultural competence).

Undoubtedly, the teaching of foreign languages and intercultural communication are closely connected and interdependent. A foreign language lesson is an intercultural practice communication, because every word is conditioned by national consciousness idea of the world. The foreign language teacher acts as an intermediary, "authorized representative" of the culture of the country of the language being studied. Even owning foreign language, it is not always possible to understand each other, and the reason for this is often is the divergence of cultures. When learning a foreign language, the student performs various activities, in the course of which he develops a number of competencies: general, communicative, and linguistic.

Each foreign language lesson is a crossroads of cultures, it is the practice of intercultural communication, because every foreign word reflects a foreign world and foreign culture: behind every word there is a national conscience (again foreign, if the word is foreign) representation of the world.

The level of knowledge of a foreign language by a student is determined not only direct contact with his teacher. To teach foreign language as a means of communication, it is necessary to create

an atmosphere of real communication, to establish connection of teaching foreign languages with life, actively use foreign languages in living, natural situations. The question of solving the actual problem of teaching foreign languages as a means communication between representatives of different peoples and cultures is that languages should be studied in inseparable unity with the world and culture of the peoples speaking in these languages.

To teach people to communicate (orally and in writing), to teach to produce, create, and not only to understand foreign speech is a difficult task, complicated by the fact that communication is not just a verbal process.

Its effectiveness, in addition to knowledge of the language, depends on many factors: conditions and culture of communication, rules of etiquette, knowledge of non-verbal forms of expression (facial expressions, gestures), the presence of deep background knowledge and much more.

Overcoming the language barrier is not enough to ensure effective communication between representatives of different cultures. To do this, you need to overcome the cultural barrier. At the following excerpt from an interesting study by I.Yu. Markovina and Yu.A. Sorokin presents national-specific components of cultures, that is, just what creates the problems of intercultural communication: “In a situation of contact representatives of different cultures (linguacultural communities) the language barrier is not the only obstacle to mutual understanding.

National-specific features of the most diverse components of culture communicators (features that make it possible for these components to implement ethnodifferentiating function) can complicate the process of intercultural communication.

To the components of culture that carry a nationally specific color, you can include at least the following:

- ❖ traditions (or enduring elements of culture) as well as customs (defined as traditions in the “socio-normative” sphere of culture) and rituals (performing the function unconscious familiarization with the normative requirements prevailing in this system);
- ❖ everyday culture, closely related to traditions, as a result of which it is often called traditional household culture;
- ❖ everyday behavior (habits of representatives of a certain culture, adopted in some social norms of communication), as well as related mimicry and pantomimic (kinesic) codes used by carriers of some linguacultural community;
- ❖ “national pictures of the world”, reflecting the specifics of the perception of the surrounding the world, national features of thinking of representatives of this or that culture;
- ❖ artistic culture, reflecting the cultural traditions of a particular ethnos [5, 142].

The native speaker of the national language and culture also has specific features. In intercultural communication, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of the national character of the communicants, the specifics of their emotional make-up, national-specific features of thinking. Intercultural learning in learning a foreign language is different from others directions of modern education. The difference is that the necessary knowledge and skills are acquired mainly through direct cultural contacts. Foreign language in this case, it is required in functional terms, as a means of communicating with people other countries. From this follows the main task of teaching foreign languages - teaching the language as a practical and complete means of communication.

In this regard, in addition to mastering foreign languages, it is important not only to know principles of intercultural communication, but also to apply and improve them on practice. A specialist graduating from a university today is a comprehensively educated person with fundamental training. A foreign language for such a specialist and a tool, and part of the culture. Professionalism of a university graduate with knowledge in the field of translation intercultural communication is based not only on an excellent knowledge of all aspects of the language, but also on the deepening of the socio-cultural component in the development communication skills.

The role of a cultural mediator, a mediator of cultures in the case of the first acquaintance of tourists with the city, most often belongs to a guide-translator who speaks the language of the guests at a fairly high level, as well as their native language. The increasing flow of tourists creates a growing demand for guide-interpreters, which, in turn, leads to an increase in the number of people who want to master this profession, and the number of schools and programs that train such specialists. In this regard, a number of questions arise: what competencies are key for representatives of this profession.

Maximum development of communication skills - this is the goal facing teachers of foreign languages. Achieving the goal of teaching people to communicate, to teach to speak a foreign language, and not just to understand foreign speech is further complicated by the fact that communication is not just a verbal process. Its effectiveness depends on many factors: the conditions and culture of communication, rules of etiquette, knowledge of non-verbal forms of expression and much more. Overcoming the language barrier is not enough to ensure effective communication between representatives of different cultures. To do this, you need to overcome the cultural barrier.

Increasing the level of training in communicative communication, communication between people different nationalities can only be achieved by understanding and taking into account sociocultural factor. One of the conditions for filling this gap is the expansion and deepening the role of the sociocultural component in the development of communicative abilities.

Communicative competence is the readiness and ability to interact, verbal and non-verbal, with other people. Therefore, the basis of all methods of communicative training should be the ability to establish connections, find successful forms of communication in any language. My pedagogical credo is "To teach, creating conditions for self-realization of each student in accordance with his interests and abilities, to maximize the satisfaction of their intellectual needs." In the process of teaching a foreign language (English) as a second language, problems arise, the main of which are the lack of a natural language environment and low motivation of students studying German when learning English as a second foreign language, since it is difficult to pronounce and understand some expressions. I wanted to interest students in various forms and methods of work in the classroom, which would allow for the effective formation of communicative competence.

According to S.G. Ter-Minasova, "to know the meanings and rules of grammar clearly not enough to actively use the language as a means of communication.

It is necessary to know as deeply as possible the world of the language being studied. Beyond values and rules grammar you need to know:

- 1) when to say / write, how, to whom, with whom, where;
- 2) as given meaning/concept, the given subject of thought lives in the reality of the language being studied" [4].

Education is the transfer to the younger generation of the culture accumulated by mankind, and foreign language culture is part of world culture.

In the lesson, I rely on the case method, i.e. I create and repeatedly play situations of authentic communication with students, for example, meeting guests at the airport, in a hotel, in a restaurant, on a bus.

The methodology for successful English teaching is based on the use of role-playing games with elements of social training. Learning is carried out through activity tasks. So, I create a case. Imagine that you are guides welcoming the guests of the World Cup. Among the guests there are athletes, coaches and spectators. Guides must meet and escort arriving guests to the bus. To do this, they need knowledge of vocabulary, speech cliches, grammatical structures. To activate vocabulary, I use the communicative training game "Roulette". To stimulate the active mental activity of children, I use an interesting exercise - Strip story. I offer students phrases, for example, on the topic "Meeting guests", and students need to try to build them logically as quickly as possible to make a dialogue. To involve all students in the process of the lesson, and to remove the psychological barrier, I use the Carousel exercise - Merry-go-round. (students form an outer and inner circle and, moving in a circle, exchange remarks). After such exercises, students will be

able to easily compose a dialogue within the framework of the case method according to the reference scheme.

Thus, a foreign language can be considered as a means of developing communicative competence. This means, first of all, the ability to adequately express communicative goals and strategies for achieving them in language forms, as well as the ability to use the norms of speech etiquette and social behavior in situations of intercultural communication, in which knowledge of the situational and sociocultural contexts of a foreign language community is analyzed. [2, 50]. The fact that the focus of the teacher's attention was on the student, his inner world, requires each teacher to have a high level of pedagogical skill, because "the lack of a child is his dignity, not disclosed by the teacher." "That teacher is good, whose words do not disagree with the deed," said Cato.

The tasks of teaching English as second language as a means of communication are inextricably merged with tasks of studying the social and cultural life of countries and peoples who speak this language. There are as many good methods as there are good teachers. (D. Poya).

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